

Study on the clinical profile of refractive amblyopic children aged 5 to 15 years: a hospital based cross-sectional study

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Abstract

Clinical Relevance:

Refractive amblyopia remains a significant but preventable cause of visual impairment in children. Timely diagnosis and intervention can greatly improve visual outcomes, underscoring the importance of understanding its clinical profile in the pediatric population.

Background:

Amblyopia is a leading cause of preventable visual impairment in children, primarily resulting from uncorrected refractive errors. This study aimed to evaluate clinical parameters of refractive amblyopic children aged 5 to 15 years.

Methods:

A cross-sectional hospital-based study was conducted among 70 children aged 5–15 years diagnosed with amblyopia. Comprehensive ophthalmic examinations were performed, including visual acuity assessment using the Snellen chart, cycloplegic refraction, slit-lamp biomicroscopy, ophthalmoscopy, and binocular status evaluation. Amblyopia was categorized based on refractive error subtypes, laterality, and underlying etiology.

Results:

The mean age of presentation was 9.47 ± 2.90 years, with 64.71% of children belonging to the 5–10 years age group. Males (60.29%) were more affected. Ocular symptoms were reported by 77.94% of children, the most common being watering (25%) and headache (22.06%), while 22.06% were asymptomatic. Compound Myopic Astigmatism (62.86%) was the most prevalent refractive error, followed by Compound Hypermetropic Astigmatism (20%). The mean Best Corrected Visual Acuity (BCVA) was 0.48 ± 0.25 log MAR in the 5–10 years group and 0.57 ± 0.20 log MAR in the 11–15 years group. Moderate amblyopia was the most common severity grade, affecting 73.17% of males and 77.78% of females. Parental awareness was the leading mode of detection (52.94%), followed by self-reporting (30.88%) and teacher identification (16.18%).

Conclusion:

Refractive amblyopia is frequently diagnosed at a late stage, with many children presenting asymptotically. Compound myopic astigmatism emerged as the predominant cause. These findings highlight the need for early screening initiatives, increased parental awareness, and school-based vision checks to facilitate timely diagnosis and management.

Keywords: Amblyopia, astigmatism, best-corrected visual acuity, refractive amblyopia, refractive error.

Introduction

Amblyopia is a visual disorder characterized by a unilateral or bilateral reduction in visual acuity that cannot be attributed to any detectable organic abnormality upon clinical examination. It is a leading cause of monocular visual impairment in children and young adults, affecting approximately 1–5% of children and 3–4% of the adult population. The condition primarily arises due to factors such as uncorrected refractive errors, strabismus, or deprivation of a clear visual image, leading to persistent visual impairment even after the correction of refractive errors. Amblyopia develops due to the suppression of neurological signals in the visual pathway of the amblyopic eye by the dominant (fellow) eye, particularly during the critical period of visual development.^{1,2} Based on its etiology, amblyopia can be classified into three main types: refractive amblyopia, strabismic amblyopia, and deprivation amblyopia. Refractive amblyopia occurs due to significant uncorrected refractive errors, such as anisometropia, where intraocular difference of best corrected visual acuity is 2 lines and more between the two eyes, is called unilateral amblyopia. where bilateral refractive bilateral amblyopia is a reduction of visual acuity lines 2 or more from the normal visual acuity bilaterally. bilateral amblyopia is uncommon and cause due to uncorrected high refractive error in both eyes, e.g., hyperopia, myopia Strabismic amblyopia results from ocular misalignment, leading to suppression of the deviated eye to avoid diplopia. Deprivation amblyopia arises from conditions that obstruct visual input, such as congenital cataracts, ptosis, or corneal opacity, preventing normal visual development.³

Early detection and timely intervention are essential for optimizing visual outcomes in affected individuals. The initial presentation of amblyopia in children varies and is typically identified through three primary mechanisms: parental detection, school screening, or self-reporting by the child. Parents may notice signs of poor vision in their child, prompting an ophthalmologic evaluation. School-based vision screenings play a crucial role in detecting amblyopia at an early stage, as teachers may identify children experiencing difficulties with visual tasks. Additionally, older children may become aware of their diminished vision and report their symptoms to caregivers or healthcare professionals. Given the importance of early diagnosis and intervention, this study aims

to investigate the clinical profile of children aged 5 to 15 years diagnosed with refractive amblyopia.⁴ The study focuses on the incidence of different clinical parameters, the distribution of various types of refractive errors, and demographic characteristics. A comprehensive understanding of the clinical profile of refractive amblyopia in this age group will facilitate improved screening, early detection, and targeted management strategies, ultimately enhancing visual outcomes in affected children.

Methods: A cross-sectional hospital-based study was conducted for 14 months after institutional ethical committee approval at the ESIC Hospital Sector 15 Rohini, New Delhi. A total of 70 patients aged from 5 to 15 years having visual acuity of 0.3 Log MAR (Snellen's visual acuity 6/12) with normal central fixations and refractive amblyopic cases whose parent / legal guardians will agree to give their consent for the study were included in the study. Whereas, strabismus children, corneal opacities, cataracts, retinal disease (visual deprivation), and children who are suffering from refractive error due to some systemic illnesses were excluded from the study.

Informed consent from parents or legal guardians was obtained before initiating the study. All the children had undergone detailed history related to the age of onset, as noticed by the patient or his guardian. Ophthalmic examination included visual acuity by Log MAR vision chart, cycloplegic refraction by streak retinoscope, auto-refractometer (Righton Speed 01), thorough anterior and posterior segment and examination by slit lamp biomicroscopy, ophthalmoscopy and assessment of the ocular alignment by cover-uncover test and ocular motility. Assessment of the binocular status of the eye was performed with the help of Worth's four –dot test and synaptophore.

The diagnostic criteria for each subtype were as follows^{5,6}:

Ametropic amblyopia: Patients exhibiting refractive errors greater than 1.0D spherical in both eyes, leading to visual acuity of Log MAR 0.30 (6/12) or worse in one or both eyes, without associated strabismus or other ocular pathologies.

Anisometric amblyopia: Defined as amblyopia occurring in the presence of anisometropia of 1.0D or more in spherical power or a difference of 1.5D or greater in

astigmatism between the two eyes. This condition persisted for over 4 weeks following spectacle correction and was not accompanied by any measurable heterophoria.

Meridional amblyopia: Patients with regular astigmatism of 1.5D or more in both eyes, leading to reduced vision in one or both eyes, without any associated strabismus. This category excluded patients with significant anisometropia, as previously defined, and a difference of 1.5D or more between the two eyes.

Statistical analysis: Data were entered into MS Excel and analyzed using SPSS software version 23. Categorical variables were shown in frequency and percentage where mean and SD was used to present continuous data.

Results: The study included a total of 68 children diagnosed with refractive amblyopia. The mean age of the study subjects was 9.47 ± 2.90 years. Among them, 44 children (64.71%) were in the 5–10 years age group, while 24 children (35.29%) were in the 11–15 years age group. Males constituted the majority of the study population (41, 60.29%), whereas females comprised 27 (39.71%).

Among the 53 children (77.94%) who reported ocular symptoms, the most common complaints were watering (25%), headache (22.06%), pain in the eye (5.88%), itching (4.41%), redness (4.41%), and irritation (4.41%). A significant proportion (22.06%) of children were asymptomatic at presentation (figure 1).

Figure 1. Distribution of ocular symptoms

The most common refractive error associated with amblyopia was Compound Myopic Astigmatism (CMA), which was observed in 62.86% of bilateral cases, 46.15% of right eye cases, and 25% of left eye cases. Other types included Compound Hypermetropic Astigmatism (CHA)(20-45%), Mixed Compound Astigmatism (MCA) (0-10%), Simple Myopia (SM)(5-7.69%), Simple Myopic Astigmatism (SMA) (0-7.69%), and Simple Hypermetropia (SH)(0-10%). P value of 0.1589 suggested that there is no significant association between types of refractive error and types of amblyopia (Table 1).

Table 1. Distribution of types of refractive error according to types of amblyopia

Type of RE	Type of amblyopia n, (%)			P-value
	Unilateral		Bilateral	
	Right eye	Left eye	Bilateral	
CMA	6 (46.15)	5 (25)	22 (62.86)	0.1589
CHA	5 (38.46)	9 (45)	7 (20)	
MCA	0 (0)	2 (10)	3 (8.57)	
SM	1 (7.69)	1 (5)	2 (5.71)	
SMA	1 (7.69)	0 (0)	1 (2.86)	
SH	0 (0)	2 (10)	0 (0)	
SHA	0 (0)	1 (5)	0 (0)	
Total	13 (100)	20 (100)	35 (100)	

CMA- Compound myopic astigmatism, CHA- Compound hypermetropic astigmatism, MCA- Mixed compound astigmatism, SM- Simple myopic, SMA- Simple myopic astigmatism, SH- Simple hypermetropia, SHA- Simple hypermetropic astigmatism

The mean BCVA in log MAR was found to be 0.48 ± 0.25 in the 5–10 years age group and 0.57 ± 0.20 in the 11–15 years age group, suggesting a trend towards worse visual acuity with increasing age however, the difference was statistically insignificant ($p = 0.0822$).

CMA was the most common ($n=25$, 56.82%) refractive error in 5-10 years age groups followed by CHA ($n=11$, 25%), MCA ($n=3$, 6.82%), and SM ($n=3$, 6.82%). While in 11-15 years age group children the most common RE was CHA seen in $n=10$ (41.67%)

cases followed by CMA (n=8, 33.33%), MCA (n=2, 8.33%), SMA (n=2, 8.33%). There was no significant association between refractive error and age (P=0.2533) (figure 2).

Figure 2. Distribution of type of refractive error according to age

CMA was the most frequent refractive error among both females (55.56%) and males (43.90%), followed by CHA. Other refractive errors were less commonly observed. There was no significant association between type of RE and sex (p=0.6634) (table 2).

Table 2. Distribution of type of refractive error according to sex

Type of RE	Sex		P-value
	Female n, (%)	Male n, (%)	
CMA	15 (55.56)	18 (43.90)	0.6634
CHA	7 (25.93)	14 (34.15)	
MCA	3 (11.11)	2 (4.88)	
SM	1 (3.70)	3 (7.32)	
SMA	0 (0)	2 (4.88)	
SH	1 (3.70)	1 (2.44)	

SHA	0 (0)	1 (2.44)	
Total	27 (100)	41 (100)	

CMA- Compound myopic astigmatism, CHA- Compound hypermetropic astigmatism, MCA- Mixed compound astigmatism, SM- Simple myopic, SMA- Simple myopic astigmatism, SH- Simple hypermetropia, SHA- Simple hypermetropic astigmatism

The majority of cases were detected by guardians (52.94%), followed by self-reporting (30.88%), and teachers (16.18%), indicating the importance of parental awareness in identifying amblyopia (table 3).

Table 3. Diminution of vision noticed by Guardian/Self/School teacher

Vision problem detected by	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Guardian	36	52.94
Self	21	30.88
Teacher	11	16.18
Total	68	100

The mean age of presentation varied with severity: Mild (8.25 ± 2.9 years), Moderate (9.09 ± 2.72 years), and Severe (10.6 ± 3.18 years) ($p = 0.1167$) (figure 3).

Figure 3. Mean age of presentation of amblyopia and its different grades

Moderate amblyopia was the most prevalent category across both males (73.17%) and females (77.78%), followed by severe amblyopia (24.39% in males and 18.52% in females), while mild amblyopia was relatively rare (2.44% in males and 3.70% in females). There was no significant difference in severity of amblyopia when compared according to sex (figure 4).

Figure 4. Distribution of severity of amblyopia according to sex

Discussion

Refractive amblyopia is one of the most common causes of preventable visual impairment in children, and early diagnosis is crucial for optimal visual outcomes. This hospital-based cross-sectional study aimed to evaluate the clinical profile of refractive amblyopic children aged 5 to 15 years.

In this study, the mean age of presentation was 9.47 ± 2.90 years, with a majority of children (64.71%) belonging to the 5–10 years age group. This age distribution aligns with the critical period for amblyopia detection and intervention, as visual development is most malleable during early childhood. Males (60.29%) outnumbered females (39.71%) in this study, consistent with previous research that suggests a higher prevalence of refractive errors in boys,^{7,8} possibly due to behavioral and genetic factors. However, some studies have shown no significant gender differences, suggesting that male predominance might not be universally observed.⁹⁻¹¹ In the Indian context, societal factors such as a gender preference for males and associated prioritization in healthcare

access may contribute to the observed male predominance. This reflects broader cultural and social dynamics influencing healthcare-seeking behavior.

Most children (77.94%) presented with ocular symptoms, the most common being watering (25%), headache (22.06%), and pain in the eye (5.88%). However, 22.06% of children were asymptomatic, highlighting the silent nature of refractive amblyopia and the need for routine eye examinations. The primary mode of detection was through guardians (52.94%), followed by self-reporting (30.88%) and teachers (16.18%). This finding reinforces the importance of parental awareness and school-based vision screening programs in detecting amblyopia at an early stage. Moreover, the primary mode of detection was through guardians (52.94%), followed by self-reporting (30.88%) and teachers (16.18%). This finding reinforces the importance of parental awareness and school-based vision screening programs in detecting amblyopia at an early stage.

The most common refractive error associated with amblyopia in this study was Compound Myopic Astigmatism (CMA), which accounted for 62.86% of bilateral cases and was the predominant type across different age groups and sexes. This aligns with previous studies that have reported a high prevalence of myopic astigmatism in amblyopic children. Compound Hypermetropic Astigmatism (CHA) was the second most common type, affecting 41.67% of older children (11–15 years), suggesting a possible delay in detection among hyperopic individuals. These findings are consistent with prior studies that highlight astigmatism as a major risk factor for amblyopia.^{7,8}

The comparison of BCVA in logMAR showed that older children (11–15 years) had worse visual acuity than younger children (5–10 years), with mean values of 0.57 ± 0.20 vs. 0.48 ± 0.25 . Though not statistically significant ($p = 0.0822$), this trend highlights the progressive nature of amblyopia when left untreated.

The study found that moderate amblyopia was the most common severity category, affecting 73.17% of males and 77.78% of females. The mean age of presentation was 8.25 years for mild amblyopia, 9.09 years for moderate, and 10.6 years for severe amblyopia. These findings are consistent with the understanding that severe amblyopia often goes unnoticed until visual impairment significantly impacts daily activities.

The findings of this study emphasize the importance of early screening and intervention to prevent long-term visual impairment due to refractive amblyopia. School vision screening programs, parental education, and regular pediatric ophthalmic examinations can aid in the early detection and management of amblyopia. Additionally, children with high-risk refractive errors, particularly astigmatism, hyperopia, and anisometropia, should undergo routine eye evaluations to facilitate early optical correction and occlusion therapy when necessary.

This study has certain limitations, including its hospital-based nature, which may not be fully representative of the general pediatric population. Additionally, factors such as compliance with treatment, socioeconomic status, and parental awareness were not assessed, which may influence amblyopia detection and management. Future studies should explore longitudinal outcomes, treatment efficacy, and associated risk factors to provide a more comprehensive understanding of refractive amblyopia in children.

Conclusion

Refractive amblyopia is a significant cause of visual impairment in children, with compound myopic astigmatism being the most common refractive error. The study underscores the need for early detection strategies, as a substantial proportion of children were asymptomatic at presentation. School-based vision screening, parental awareness, and timely ophthalmologic intervention are crucial in reducing the burden of amblyopia and improving visual outcomes in affected children.

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